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ACADEMIC MENTORSHIP AND LECTURERS' PRODUCTIVITY IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This paper examined academic mentorship and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria with an adopted correlation design and using the Taro Yamane technique to draw a sample size of 354 respondents from a population of 3,110 academic staff in four public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. Three research questions were raised, and three null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The research instruments titled: 'Academic Mentorship Questionnaire' (AMQ) and 'Lecturers' Productivity Questionnaire' (LPQ) were used for data for answering the research questions and hypotheses. The reliability of the instruments was 0.67 and 0.70 coefficient using Cronbach's alpha. Kendall's tau-b correlation was used to analyse data collected via Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 22.0. findings of the hypotheses 1, 2 and 3 showed that a significant relationship existed between academic staff mentorship on teaching and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria ($\tau_b = .662$; $N=354$; $p<0.05$); a significant relationship existed between academic staff mentorship on research and lecturers' productivity in public universities Lagos State, Nigeria ($\tau_b = .671$; $N=354$; $p<0.05$); and a significant relationship existed between academic staff mentorship on community services and lecturers' productivity in public universities Lagos State, Nigeria ($\tau_b = .589$; $N=354$; $p<0.05$). Based on the findings, the study concluded that mentorship of junior academic staff by senior academics helps to sustain academic integrity and excellence in the Nigerian university system. Therefore, it is recommended that a mentorship policy should be developed by the university management to establish structure and functions for a sustainable mentorship programme for all junior lecturers in the university towards achieving the core value of teaching, research and community service.

Keywords: Academic Staff, Mentorship, Productivity, Teaching and Research

Introduction

In recent times, there seems to be a paradigm shift in University education which is mentorship based. This is because mentorship has become a critical factor affecting the university system toward achieving academic excellence. In academia, mentorship programmes are designed for academic staff, Non-academic staff and students. The mentorship programmes for academic staff or lecturers majorly help to attain the University

Vision and Mission which is anchored on the advancement of academic excellence through teaching, research, and community service. In the University system, a mentor is a role model, experienced person and professional expert who shares expertise knowledge, skills, and experience with a mentee or protégé about career path and provides leadership, guidance, motivation, and emotional support to increase individual effectiveness and efficiency in the organisation. According to Nnaji et al. (2015), the mentor should be people-oriented, open-minded, flexible, empathetic, collaborative, willing to make time and space for productive discussions, establish an equitable relationship and so on. These are obvious activities that require time and commitment. Mentoring is a one-on-one connection between an expert (the Mentor) and a younger, less experienced individual (the Protégé), with the goal of the Mentor willingly committing time to teach, support, and encourage the Protégé. According to Popoola, Adesopo and Ajayi (2013), mentoring is the process whereby an experienced and highly empathic person called the mentor, assists, and guides another individual called the protégé (whether male or female) in the development of their skills, knowledge and attitudes and their competence in the workplace.

However, mentoring, which is the practice of a senior expert teaching a junior one in the workplace, is getting harder, especially in the university system. The term was first used in 1616 and it implies a teacher (Cartwright, 2012). In the university system which is the focus of this study, academic mentors seem to be senior academics who must share expertise knowledge, wisdom and understanding with junior academics and guide proteges on career paths, developing contacts, setting goals and offering personal support toward the attainment of academic excellence. Mentoring of protégé in the University is a collegial system for building a Centre of academic excellence seminars, conferences and workshops are all used to acquire knowledge at universities, which are known as citadels of learning. Olasupo (2011) states that an academic mentor is usually a senior faculty member who guides a junior faculty member by way of advice, guidance, support and other relevant means in matters connected to the attainment of academic success; the protégé, on the other hand, is the junior faculty member who is the beneficiary of the mentorship. Generally, it has been agreed that mentoring is one of the easiest and most effective methods of assisting individuals to develop the required skill sets in different organizations (Olasupo, 2011; Olowookere, 2012; Okurame, 2008; Ojokuku & Sajuyigbe, 2015; Sola, 2018). The prevailing consensus in Nigeria is that the "younger generation" is to blame for the rapidly deteriorating academic quality that the nation once had in its educational system (Ndaguba et al., 2018). It has been observed that the productivity of academic staff in public universities in Lagos State has been persistently decline due to inadequate mentorship training and programme in some ivory tower.

Statement of the Problem

Recently, public university education in Nigeria has become worrisome and bedevilled with challenges of mentorship which culminated in huge lecturers' turnover and brain-drain syndrome. Incidentally, several factors have been observed as clogs on the wheels of progress of academic mentorship and hindered teaching, research and community service for attainment university vision and mission in Nigeria. Particularly, public university academic staff has been bedeviled with mentorship practices where preferred mentors sometimes decline protégés' requests for mentorships. Some senior academics who ought to act as mentors to junior academics are hardly available and accessible. Academic staff are categorized into senior academic staff (Professors; Associate Professors; and Senior Lecturers) and junior academic staff (Lecturer I; Lecturer II; Assistant Lecturers and Graduate Assistants). Many professors are either on sabbatical in other universities, on leave

of absence, or are busy as adjunct lecturers, external examiners and consultants elsewhere. This creates a situation where the junior academic staff are left without mentors to whom they can relate in their area of specialization which on teaching, research, and community service. The senior academics hurriedly attend to proteges when they are available; they are saddled with other university responsibilities such as Deanships, Directorates, Headships and other positions within the university that make it difficult for them to have a meaningful mentoring relationship with their protégés if they have any. Similarly, other factors like gender, age, qualification and work experience adversely affected mentorship practice. Gender bias is acknowledged as a significant obstacle in mentoring relationships since mentees may be wary of developing romantic ties with the mentor. perhaps, there's a chance that protege won't have many options for their desired gender.

The Objective of the Study

The objective of this study was to:

1. examine the relationship between academic staff mentorship on teaching and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.
2. determine the relationship between academic staff mentorship on research and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.
3. assess the relationship between academic staff mentorship on community services and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

The following Null hypotheses were raised:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between academic staff mentorship on teaching and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between academic staff mentorship on research and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between academic staff mentorship on community services and lecturers' productivity in public universities Lagos State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The research design was descriptive survey and correlational. The target population comprised all 3,110 lecturers in the University of Lagos, Akoka (UNILAG); Lagos State University, Ojo (LASU); Lagos State University of Education. The sample size comprised 354 lecturers randomly selected using Taro Yamane sampling techniques for the study. A structured instrument titled: Academic Mentorship Questionnaire' (AMQ) and Lecturers' Productivity Questionnaire (LPQ) were designed by the researcher. The questionnaires were administered to all selected lecturers in the Faculty of Social Sciences, Faculty of Education, Faculty of Art, Faculty of Science, Faculty of Engineering, and Faculty of management science in four universities under study. 88 lecturers were randomly selected from each university and 15 lecturers were selected from each of the faculties selected for the study. The questionnaire was divided into two sections: Section A and B. Section A contains the personal information of the respondents and B contains the questionnaire items structured around the search questions. Each statement is measured on a four-point modifier Likert-type-rating scale, namely: "Strongly Agree (SA) on 4points", "Agree (A) on 3 points", "Strongly Disagree (SD) on 2 points" and "Disagree (D) on 1point". The data collected were properly analyzed using Kendall's tau-b correlation coefficient. The content validity of the instruments was scrutinized by test experts and the reliability index of the instrument was

persistently determined through Cronbach’s alpha at 0.67 and 0.70 meaning that the instrument is reliable.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Kendall's tau-b correlation analysis between academic staff mentorship on teaching and lecturers’ productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Variables		Correlations		
			Academic Staff Mentorship on Teaching	Lecturers’ Productivity
Kendall's tau_b	Academic Staff_ Mentorship on Teaching	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.662
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.001
		N	354	354
	Lecturers'_Productivity	Correlation Coefficient	.662	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.
		N	354	354

Source: Field Survey (2023) * Correlation was significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)*

A Kendall's tau-b correlation was run to investigate the relationship between academic staff mentorship on teaching and lecturers’ productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. The result indicated that there was a strong, positive correlation relationship between academic staff mentorship on teaching and lecturers’ productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. ($\tau_b = .662$; $N=354$; $p<0.05$). Hence, the hypothesis which stated that “there is no significant relationship between academic staff mentorship on teaching and lecturers’ productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria is rejected and alternate was accepted. The p-value of 0.001 is less than the 0.05 significance level which indicated the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implied that a statistically, significant relationship existed between academic staff mentorship on teaching and lecturers’ productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. This finding negates Undiyaundeye and Basake’s (2017) that the challenges to effective mentoring in academia include the inability and unwillingness of young academics to follow instructions from mentors, due to the "get rich quick" mentality, the inability of the institution to manage personnel and ensure good community partnerships, inability and unwillingness of the mentors to support subordinate professional growth and finally, the inability of the school management to sanction untoward behaviour by young academics due to godfatherism.

Table 2: Kendall's tau-b correlation analysis between academic staff mentorship on research and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Variables		Correlations		
			Academic Staff Mentorship on Research	Lecturers' Productivity
Kendall's tau_b	Academic Staff_Mentorship on Research	Correlation	1.000	.671
		Coefficient		
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.001
	Lecturers'_Productivity	N	354	354
		Correlation	.671	1.000
		Coefficient		
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.
		N	354	354

Source: Field Survey (2023) * Correlation was significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)*

A Kendall's tau-b correlation was run to investigate the relationship between academic staff mentorship on research and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. The result indicated that there was a strong, positive correlation relationship between academic staff mentorship on research and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. ($\tau_b = .671$; $N=354$; $p<0.05$). Hence, the hypothesis which stated that "there is no significant relationship between academic staff mentorship on research and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria is rejected and an alternate was accepted. The p-value of 0.001 is less than the 0.05 significance level which indicated the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implied that a statistically, significant relationship existed between academic staff mentorship on research and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. This finding was supported by Nnaji et al. (2015) that the mentor should be people-oriented, open-minded, flexible, empathetic, collaborative, willing to make time and space for productive discussions, establish an equitable relationship and so on.

Table 3: Kendall's tau-b correlation analysis between academic staff mentorship on community service and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Variables		Correlations		
			Academic Staff Mentorship on Community Service	Lecturers' Productivity
Kendall's tau_b	Academic Staff_Mentorship on community service	Correlation	1.000	.589
		Coefficient		
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.001
	Lecturers'_Productivity	N	354	354
		Correlation	.589	1.000
		Coefficient		
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.
		N	354	354

Source: Field Survey (2023) * Correlation was significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)*

A Kendall's tau-b correlation was run to investigate the relationship between academic staff mentorship on community service and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. The result indicated that there was a strong, positive correlation relationship between academic staff mentorship on community service and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. ($\tau_b = .589$; $N=354$; $p<0.05$). Hence, the hypothesis which stated that "there is no significant relationship between academic staff mentorship on community service and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria is rejected, and an alternate was accepted. The p-value of 0.001 is less than the 0.05 significance level which indicated the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implied that a statistically, significant relationship existed between academic staff mentorship on community service and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Conclusion

The university is an ivory tower and citadel of learning where teaching, research and community service can be achieved through mentorship programmes. Some public universities in Nigeria suffer a huge setback in mentorship programmes toward the attainment of academic excellence. Based on the findings of this study, academic staff mentorship in teaching, research and community service contributes significantly toward achieving high productivity of lecturers. Therefore, academic excellence can be attained if the university authority organises seminars, conferences and workshops on mentorship programmes for junior academic staff. The study concluded that academic mentorship is a major predictor of lecturers' productivity in public universities in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Universities through the Deans and HODs of various departments should intensify efforts in making mentorship programmes a top priority.
2. Universities management should organise a central mentorship programme for junior academic staff and ensure that expertise and skills are passed to the less experienced staff.
3. Universities should make it mandatory that every older/experienced lecturer should have a junior staff (lecturer) to mentor, provided that the older colleague(s) has the type of personality/charisma required for successful mentoring.
4. Universities via the HODs should initiate modalities whereby stored knowledge and information can be easily accessed. This is crucial because knowledge and information that is not accessible are of no benefit to mankind.
5. The government should create an enabling environment for knowledge management to thrive.

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